

Synthesis and Acetone Sensing Properties of Porous CeO₂ Nano particles.

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Abstract

CeO₂ Nano particles with a porous morphology were successfully prepared through solution combustion method at 400°C with subsequent calcination. X-ray diffraction confirms the formation of crystalline phase along with particle size less than 22nm. The field-emission scanning electron microscopy reveals the surface morphology of the material, EDAX and UV were used to analyse the elemental composition and optical band gap prepared samples respectively. Gas sensing analysis revealed that the CeO₂ sensor showed excellent response and selectivity to acetone with quick response and recovery times, which might substantially benefit from their distinctive porous structure and large surface area.

Keywords

CeO₂ nano particles; Acetone; Gas sensors